

Impact of Climate Change on Animal Husbandry

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Abstract

By 2050, the demand for animal products is anticipated to double globally, largely as a result of rising living standards everywhere. Climate change has both direct and indirect effects on livestock, such as heat stress and increased morbidity and mortality. While the demand for livestock products is predicted to grow double by the middle of the twenty-first century. Climate change poses a threat to livestock production through competition for natural resources, quantity and quality of feeds, livestock diseases, heat stress, and biodiversity loss. Climate change is accelerated by the cattle industry, which produces 14.5% of the world's greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. As a result, the cattle industry will play a significant role in reducing GHG emissions and enhancing global food security.

Introduction

By 2050, it is predicted that there will be 9.6 billion human population on the planet, which will up from 7.2 billion now. This is to be a 33% increase in human population on the earth, while the demand for agricultural products is expected to rise by nearly 70% during the same time period as the global standard of living rises. Since 1991, worldwide the total area of cultivated land has remained stable, despite of improved productivity and intensification initiatives in agricultural sector and it supply 33% of the world's protein intake and

17% of the world's calorie consumption. Livestock products are a crucial agricultural product for maintaining global food security.

Nearly, 1.1 billion people are employed in the livestock industry, which supports the livelihoods of one billion of the world's poorest people. The "livestock revolution" has been coined to describe the quick rise in demand for livestock products in developing nations. In 2050, a rise of 1077 million tonnes in milk output and 455 million tonnes in meat production are estimated globally.

Climate change, the struggle for land and water, and food security during a time of greatest needs are all expected to have a negative impact on livestock output. The main source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, which warm the atmosphere, are responsible for global climate change. According to Gerber *et al.* (2013), the cattle industry generates 14.5% of the world's greenhouse gas emissions, which might lead to increased land degradation, air and water pollution, and reductions in biodiversity.

Green House Gas Emissions

Global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from the livestock industry are largely made up of methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and carbon dioxide. Livestock supply chains are a substantial source of these emissions (CO₂). Anthropogenic GHG emissions are primarily made up of methane (44%), followed by nitrous oxide (29%) and carbon dioxide (27%). The emissions (39%) from the cattle industry are attributable to enteric fermentation, a normal component of the digestive process for many ruminant animals. Manure storage (10%), feed production and processing (45%) are additional substantial sources of emissions. The processing and transportation of livestock products is responsible for the remaining 6% of GHG emissions. Higher levels of these gases can be attributed to livestock systems that are less productive and efficient due to excessive losses of organic matter, nutrients, and energy.

More greenhouse gas emissions are released into the environment through the production of livestock than from the entire world's transportation industry. The cattle industry contributes to greenhouse gas emissions both directly and indirectly through factors like animal physiology, housing, waste storage, waste treatment, land application, and chemical fertilizers. Enteric fermentation, respiration, and excretions are three examples of direct emissions from animal sources.

Indirect emissions are those produced by feed crops, irrigation practices, farm activities, the processing of animal products, transportation, and the allotment of land for the raising of livestock (e.g., deforestation, desertification, carbon released from cultivated soils). More carbon is released into the environment as a result of indirect emissions than direct emissions in the livestock industry. However, the geography and type of farming system have a different impact on GHG emissions. The main causes of CO₂ emissions include deforestation, cultivated soils, and land degradation brought on by animal rearing. 9.2% of the total GHG emissions from livestock are linked to changes in land use, of which 6% are the result of expanding pastures and 3.2% are the result of expanding feed crops.

Livestock provides 44% of global anthropogenic methane emissions through regular digestive processes (enteric fermentation) and waste management. Enteric fermentation transforms the ingested feed into digestible feed throughout the animals' digestive process. Through exhalation, enteric fermentation produces the byproduct CH₄. Methane and nitrous oxide are gases released by livestock's dung. Methane is produced during the anaerobic breakdown of the organic compounds found in waste. Nitrous oxide emissions are often increased by the use of fertilizers, agricultural nitrogen fixation, and atmospheric nitrogen deposition. Land use change, feed production, animal production, waste, and processing and transport all have an impact on climate. Methane, nitrous oxide, and carbon dioxide are released during the manufacture of waste and feed, which has an impact on climate change. While the demand for livestock products is predicted to rise by 100% by the middle of the twenty-first century, climate change will affect livestock production through competition for natural resources, quantity and quality of feeds, livestock illnesses, heat stress, and biodiversity loss.

Maintaining a balance between productivity, domestic food security, and environmental protection is thus a challenge.

Growing and reproducing animals are significantly more at risk from higher temperatures than they are from a cold environment. Animal performance is compromised by temperatures above the upper critical level due to altered energy and nutrient metabolism as well as disturbed homeostasis, which has negative effects on both immune function and product quality. In general speaking, livestock with high potential for output are most susceptible to heat stress.

Climate-Smart Livestock

Through increased livestock productivity, effective use of natural resources, carbon sequestration, and incorporation of livestock into the circular bio-economy, climate-smart livestock (CSL) solutions can help reduce GHG emissions. Implementing Climate Smart Livestock at the farm level while taking into account three goals i.e. by sustainably increasing productivity, adapting to climate change and by reducing GHG emissions. Improved productivity, lower GHG emissions, and climate change adaptation are all benefits of good livestock management. Since enteric fermentation is the primary cause of direct GHG emissions, therefore, it is advised to keep using strategies that try to make the feed basket better. Methane emissions from animals can be decreased by increasing the quantity of concentrate (high energy feeds containing cereal grains and oil meals) in the animal's diet. Through better grazing land management, improved pasture species, changing forage mix, and increased use of feed supplements to achieve a balanced diet, including crop by-products and processing of crop residues, it is possible to improve feed digestibility and energy content and better match protein supply to animal requirements. These actions can enhance nutrient absorption, boost animal productivity and fertility

which may reduce emissions per unit of product. Improved yields per hectare, higher water productivity, efficient use of low-carbon energy, and a reduction in waste along the value chain are some important characteristics of climate-smart livestock that concentrate on the effective use of natural resources.

Conclusion

GHG emissions are decreased by well-managed mixed agricultural and animal systems. The climate-smart farms produce more milk while lowering its GHG emissions and building up its carbon stores. A higher-quality animal products include less methane per unit of calories, protein, and digestibility in the feed. The use of methane inhibitors seems to be very effective but would need to be proven in the tropics, which is another possible option. It has also a higher concentration of condensed tannins, which improves nutrient absorption, leguminous forages produce high-quality feed and lowers methane emissions. The adoption of scientific and well managed practices in animal husbandry will play a significant indirect role in enhancing global food security to tackle increasing human population challenges in future.

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